

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

CRYSTAL STRUCTURE AND MICRODEFORMATION OF COMPOSITES BASED ON ZIRCONIUM DIOXIDE AND WOLLASTONITE

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Abstract

The synthesis and characterization of crystal structure and microdeformation of ceramic composites based on zirconium dioxide and wollastonite system have been investigated. The results revealed that the influence of sintering temperature and an increase in the content of wollastonite was established to affect the change in the formation of crystal structure and lattice parameters, complex phase composition, phase transformations in this system. It was shown that a decrease in the crystallite size of zirconium oxide leads to change in microstrain of ZrO_2 (MgO) – $CaSiO_3$.

Keywords: crystal structure, lattice parameters, composite, zirconium dioxide, wollastonite.

I. INTRODUCTION

As mentioned earlier, zirconium dioxide and wollastonite have unique properties and are widely used in various industries [1–5]. However, there are insufficient data in the literature on the parameters of the fine crystal structure and the phase composition of the material based on ZrO_2 -MgO obtained with the addition of wollastonite.

Thus, it is possible to create porous materials based on zirconium dioxide, and in this case the porous structure can play the role of effective regions of relaxation of stress concentrators arising under mechanical loading. Another option for maintaining the mechanical strength of the material with increasing temperature is the introduction of a second phase, especially in the form of fibers. For these purposes, it is possible to use a natural compound - wollastonite. However, there are practically no studies devoted to the zirconium dioxide-wollastonite system, although this system may be promising for the creation of composites for various functional purposes, for example, heat-insulating, biomedical, and other materials.

Literature data are known that describe the properties, crystal structure, phase composition of zirconium dioxide and individual systems created on its basis. For example, Aksay I.A. and Pask J.A found that ZrO_2 exists in three crystalline modifications: tetragonal, monoclinic and cubic; revealed that it is possible to change the temperatures of phase transitions and the

value of the temperature interval in which the phase transformation occurs [6, 7]. According to the studies of Betz U., Sturm A., Loeffler J.F., Wagner W., Wiedenmann A., Hahn H. [8 - 10], the kinetics of phase transformations and the growth of crystallites during the thermal treatment of ceramic powders are greatly influenced not only by the type, but also the amount of the stabilizer, which can lead to a change in the boundaries of the temperature interval of the tetragonal monoclinic phase transition [11–13]. De Aza P.N., Luklinska Z.B., Anseau M.R. made a significant contribution to the development of ideas about the regularities of the ceramics of the composite based on ZrO_2 - $CaSiO_3$. [14]. Ceramic composites based on β - $CaSiO_3$ - ZrO_2 (3Y) are described by Lihua Long, Faming Shang, Lei Chen, Lidong Chen, and Jiang Chang [15]. Their research contributed greatly to the study of the physical and mechanical properties of ceramics based on zirconium dioxide-wollastonite with the aim of using it as a bioactive material for the manufacture of orthopedic products, as well as to improve the mechanical properties of biopolymers due to high bioactivity and biocompatibility.

However, at present, a number of issues related to the study of the ZrO_2 - $CaSiO_3$ system remain open, including phase formation, structure, morphology, particle size of zirconium dioxide powders and ceramics based on them, which can vary significantly depending on the amount and type of stabilizing additive.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to synthesis and characterization of crystal structure and lattice parameters of ceramic composites based on zirconium dioxide and wollastonite.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

ZrO₂-MgO powders were used as materials for research, obtained by the decomposition of liquid precursors in high-frequency plasma were used as materials for research [16]. Wollastonite is a mineral whose chemical composition includes calcium, silicon and oxygen. The samples were pressed into a cylindrical shape on cold isostatic pressing with compacting hydraulic pressure 300 MPa. The samples were sintered at different temperatures 1000-1650°C in the furnace. The heating rate was used during the sintering at a maximum

heating rate of 5°C per minute and a maximum cooling rate of 10°C per minute.

The phase analysis, crystalline size, and lattice parameters of samples were determined by X-ray diffraction (XRD). X-ray diffraction analysis was carried out using CuK α ($\lambda = 1.54178$ nm) radiation source at a voltage of 40 kV and a current of 20 mA. Continuous scanning was carried out from 15° as 2 θ start position to 120° as 2 θ end position, with a step size of 0.05 and step time of 1 sec. The duration of an X-ray exposure at each point has enough to produce, a relative error on the background count rate of less than 3%. The relative size of the coherence length (CL) was carried out by the broadening of the most intense X-ray reflections at small-angle scattering and diffraction [17].

(a)

(b)

Fig 1. SEM images powders (a) zirconia (b) natural wollastonite

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dependence of the maximum intensity half-width of monoclinic zirconium dioxide, monoclinic wollastonite modification, and triclinic wollastonite modification on the sintering temperature is calculated. Analysis of the data showed that the crystallite size of

tetragonal zirconium (t-ZrO₂) in the {111} peak varied from 26 to 77 nm; it should be noted that the crystallite size increased at a temperature of 1000–1300°C. The sizes of crystallites of cubic zirconium (c-ZrO₂) in the {111} peak varied from 19 to 38 nm.

Fig 2. Change in the size of crystallite phases in ZrO₂ (MgO) –1%CaSiO₃ composites at different sintering temperatures

It can be seen that the size of cubic zirconium crystals depends on the sintering temperature. The crystallite size of monoclinic zirconia (m-ZrO₂) was higher at a lower temperature of 1000°C. In this case, the sizes of m-ZrO₂ crystallites in the {111} peak varied from 32 to 67 nm, m-ZrO₂ in the {11-1} peak varied from 31 to

65 nm, and m-ZrO₂ in the {21-1} peak varied from 28 up to 55 nm, at a sintering temperature from 1000 to 1650°C. Figure 2 shows the change in the size of phase crystallites in composites (1 vol.% CaSiO₃) at different sintering temperatures.

Fig 3. Change in the size of crystallites (nm) of the monoclinic phase of zirconium dioxide, determined from the lines {111} and {11-1}, with a change in the sintering temperature

Thus, it should be noted that there is an intense interaction between the components of the composite material, which leads to a change in the size of the zirconium dioxide crystallites. It can be seen that at a temperature of 1100–1300°C, a sharp change in the size of

crystallites in the zirconium dioxide phases is observed. This is consistent with the range of interplanar spacing $d\{11-1\}$, $d\{111\}$ of monoclinic zirconia and depends on the sintering temperature.

Fig 4. Dependence of the sizes of crystallites of the triclinic phase of wollastonite, determined from the {131} lines, on the sintering temperature and its content in the initial mixture

The change in the size of crystallites of the monoclinic modification of wollastonite (m-CaSiO₃) in the {140} peak ranged from 26 to 44 nm, in the {-431} peak varied from 21 to 45 nm, and the triclinic modification of wollastonite (t-CaSiO₃) in the {-313} varied from 27 to 42 nm, and also in the {131} peak varied from 27 to 53 nm, at different temperatures and concentrations of wollastonite. The size of crystallites in wollastonite phases also decreases with increasing sintering temperature; this anomalous behavior is due to the interaction between zirconium and wollastonite. In this case, the grain size dispersion also decreases,

which indicates the formation of a more homogeneous structure with an increase in the CaSiO₃ content.

The analysis of the physical broadening of X-ray reflections determined the microdeformation of the crystal lattice of the ceramics of the "zirconium dioxide - wollastonite" system. Microstrains calculated from the diffraction maximum of the {21-1}, {11-1} peaks of monoclinic zirconia, as well as in the {140}, {-431} peaks of the wollastonite monoclinic modification, and in the {-313}, {131} peaks of the triclinic modifications of wollastonite.

Fig 5. Change in microstrain $(\varepsilon^2)^{1/2}$ depending on the crystallite size (OCD) of the monoclinic modification of wollastonite in sintered composites (microstrain was calculated from the diffraction maximum {140}, and the crystallite size (OCD) was calculated from the {-431} peak of the monoclinic modification of CaSiO₃)

Relative changes in the microdeformation of the crystal lattice ($(\varepsilon^2)^{1/2}$ of monoclinic zirconium dioxide (m-ZrO₂) in the {21-1} peak varied from 0.012 to 0.0155. It should be noted that at temperatures from 1200 to 1300°C, the m-ZrO₂{21-1} microstrain significantly increased in the samples in which the volume content of CaSiO₃ was 1 and 5 and amounted to 0.0155. It has been established that at a sintering temperature

from 1100 to 1300°C, intense interfacial interaction is observed in composite materials between zirconium dioxide and wollastonite, which leads to a change in the crystallite size and microdeformation of the crystal lattice of the composite. It was shown that the values of microdeformations of the crystal lattice depending on the sintering temperature and the number of wollastonite fibers in the composite mixture.

Fig 6. Dependence of microdeformation $(\varepsilon^2)^{1/2}$ on the crystallite size (OCD) of monoclinic zirconium dioxide in sintered composites (microdeformation was calculated from the diffraction maximum {21-1}, and the OCD crystallite size was calculated from the {11-1} peak of the monoclinic modification of ZrO₂)

It has been established that the change in microstrain $(\varepsilon^2)^{1/2}$ of monoclinic zirconia depends on the crystallite size (OCD) of monoclinic zirconia.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

It was shown that the sizes of zirconium oxide and wollastonite crystallites decrease with an increase in the sintering temperature from 1100 to 1300°C. Apparently, interfacial interaction, which manifests itself in a change in the structural state of zirconium dioxide, should lead to changes in the size of its crystallites, crystal structure parameters, phases, and lattice parameters in sintered samples [18]. With an increase in the sintering temperature, the size of the crystallites decreases. The presence of lattice defects in materials with macroscopic properties is shown. It can be seen that, as the size of zirconium oxide crystallites changes, the microdeformation of the ZrO₂ crystal lattice changes, while the microdeformation of the CaSiO₃ lattice does not depend on the crystallite size [19, 20].

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METHODS OF DETERMINING LIMITING DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS OF TWO-COMPONENT METALLIC SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The paper describes the methods of determining the limiting coefficient of distribution, as one of the main parameters for evaluating the efficiency of deep refining of metals by crystallization methods. Experimental, calculation and graphical methods of determining the limiting coefficients of distribution in metal systems for different types of solubility are described. The determination methods for systems with limited solubility of components in the solid phase and with extremely low solubility are considered. The calculations of this parameter are performed for binary systems based on Cd, Zn, Te, Zr, Hf, and Ti. The results of graphical methods of determining the limiting coefficient of distribution for such systems as Ag–Mg, Ni–Ga, Mg–Al, Nb–Ge are presented.

Keywords: distribution coefficients, binary state diagrams, solubility of components, methods for determining limiting coefficient of distribution.

Introduction

During liquid-solid phase transitions for two-component systems, the interphase distribution coefficients (DC) of the components are important parameters. Therefore, when solving practical problems, there is often a need for an approximate estimate of unknown DC. Among the known DC, such as the effective (EFDC) k_{ef} and the equilibrium (EDC) k_{0B}^A , it is important for practical and computational applications (for example, for estimating the limiting solubility of poorly soluble components, calculating the solidus lines of binary eutectic systems, determining the thermodynamic parameters of the solubility of components, etc.) has the limiting coefficient of distribution (LCD) k_{0limB}^A . LCD characterizes the interphase distribution of the second component near the melting temperature of the main component, that is, with a low concentration of the impurity element. The value of this parameter provides a guideline for evaluating the efficiency of deep refining of metals by the method of directional crystallization

(DCr). The purpose of this paper is to review the methods of determining k_{0limB}^A and to provide examples of the application of these methods for the calculation of the limiting distribution coefficients for individual binary systems.

1. Characteristics of the distribution coefficients of two-component metallic systems

One of the methods of deep cleaning of metals at the final stage is DCr. An important parameter characterizing the behavior of an impurity during purification by the DCr method is the DC of the impurity. Based on the known values of DC, it is possible to pre-plan the crystallization purification process and estimate the achievable purity of the refined metal.

The definitions of the characteristics of EFDC, EDC, LCD were given, for example, in [1]. The EDC were determined by the thermodynamic properties of the main component A and impurities at a crystallization rate equal to or close to zero. The EDC values were found, as a rule, from double state diagrams (SD)